

The Philippines

Introduction

Under the United Nations' Agenda 2030, one indicator of progress towards the conservation of mountain ecosystems (SDG 15.4) is the percentage [%] coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity (**key biodiversity areas, KBAs**) by **protected areas (PAs)** (SDG 15.4.1). KBAs are areas that significantly contribute to the persistence of global biodiversity. Currently, the indicator is hosted by the UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (WCMC).

WCMC site-based: The indicator is officially calculated as the **average of the PA coverage of KBAs within a country that are considered mountainous** based on the WCMC mountain definition from 2000¹.

GMBA area-based: As an alternative, the Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (GMBA) calculates the indicator as the **ratio between the total area of protected KBAs and the total area of KBAs in mountains**, applying its latest mountain definition from 2022².

Unless mentioned otherwise, the data presented in this one-pager correspond to the GMBA area-based calculation approach, for countries that have KBA in mountains (n = 190).

WCMC site-based versus GMBA area-based (temporal comparison)

The Philippines in an international context (2020)

In the left side figure, each point represents one country and its indicator value with both the WCMC site-based and the GMBA area-based calculation approach. The Philippines is marked with the asterisk. Countries close to the diagonal line have a similar indicator value for both calculation approaches, not taking into account the mountain area of a country.

The Philippines, with a GMBA area-based **indicator value of 40.3 for 2020**, has a value lower than 110 other countries. 79 countries have a value lower than the Philippines.

¹ Kapos et al. (2000) doi:10.1079/9780851994468.0004

² Snethlage et al. (2022) doi:10.1038/s41597-022-01256-y

015-17-03

Subnational indicator values

From the 49 mountain ranges in the Philippines, five are without KBA (pinkish coloring in the country map). From the other 44 (left side figure), seven have an indicator value of at least 95%, with one being fully protected.

Explore GMBA's global coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity by protected areas, visit:
gmba.unibe.ch/services/indicators/sdg_1541